

Review

Animal experimental models of ischemic limbs – A systematic review

Veronika Lovasova^{a,b,*}, Robert Bem^c, Jaroslav Chlupac^{a,e}, Michal Dubsky^{c,d},
Jitka Husakova^{c,d}, Andrea Nemcova^c, Jiri Fronck^{a,d,e}

^a Transplant Surgery Department, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic

^b Second Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

^c Diabetes Centre, Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Prague, Czech Republic

^d First Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

^e Department of Anatomy, Second Faculty of Medicine, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Background: The objective of this systematic review is to summarize the available animal models of ischemic limbs, and to provide an overview of the advantages and disadvantages of each animal model and individual method of limb ischemia creation.

Methods: A review of literature was conducted using the PubMed and Web of Science pages. Various types of experimental animals and surgical approaches used in creating ischemic limbs were evaluated. Other outcomes of interest were the specific characteristics of the individual experimental animals, and duration of tissue ischemia.

Results: The most commonly used experimental animals were mice, followed by rabbits, rats, pigs, miniature pigs, and sheep. Single or double arterial ligation and excision of the entire femoral artery was the most often used method of ischemic limb creation. Other methods comprised single or double arterial electrocoagulation, use of ameroid constrictors, photochemically induced thrombosis, and different types of endovascular methods. The shortest duration of tissue ischemia was 7 days, the longest 90 days.

Conclusions: This review shows that mice are among the most commonly used animals in limb ischemia research. Simple ligation and excision of the femoral artery is the most common method of creating an ischemic limb; nevertheless, it can result in acute rather than chronic ischemia. A two-stage sequential approach and methods using ameroid constrictors or endovascular blinded stent grafts are more suitable for creating a gradual arterial occlusion typically seen in humans. Selecting the right mouse strain or animal with artificially produced diabetes or hyperlipidaemia is crucial in chronic ischemic limb research. Moreover, the observation period following the onset of ischemia should last at least 14 days, preferably 4 weeks.

Creating an suitable in vivo model of limb ischemia is an important basis of preclinical studies of therapeutic angiogenesis, which aim to improve wound healing in “no-option” patients with chronic limb-threatening ischemia and diabetic ulcers. Unfortunately, there is a lack of a validated preclinical animal models of chronic wound healing that correlates well with human critical limb ischemia. The aim of this review is to help researchers choosing an optimal model of chronic ischemic tissue, which would resemble human chronic arterial obstructive lesions as similar as possible.

1. Introduction

The most severe stage of peripheral arterial disease (PAD), chronic limb-threatening ischemia (CLTI), causes pain at rest, ulceration, and gangrene [1]. The clinical manifestation of CLTI depends on the degree of ischemia, the presence of infection, and neuropathy [2]. Treatment options are usually limited to surgical or endovascular revascularization or limb amputation [3].

Diabetes mellitus (DM) and smoking are the major risk factors for

Abbreviations: ApoE^{-/-} mice, Apolipoprotein E deficient mice; CLTI, chronic limb-threatening ischemia; DM, diabetes mellitus; EIA, external iliac artery; FA, femoral artery; GH, growth hormone; IA, iliac artery; IGF-1, insulin-like growth factor-1; IIA, internal iliac artery; PAD, peripheral arterial disease; RFA, radiofrequency ablation.

* Corresponding author at: Institute for Clinical and Experimental Medicine, Transplant Surgery Department, Videnska 1958/9, 140 21 Prague, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: veronika.lovasova@ikem.cz (V. Lovasova).

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atherosclerotic disease [4]. According to Alexiadou et al. [5], 40–70% of all lower limb nontraumatic amputations occur in diabetic patients. One-third of patients with diabetic foot ulcers have ischemia [6]. New and advanced therapies are urgently needed to address slow healing and frequent relapse [7].

Novel interventions aim to improve blood flow to the lower limbs and promote blood vessel growth through arteriogenesis or angiogenesis [8]. A reliable and reproducible animal model is needed in order to clarify the cellular and molecular mechanisms underlying the neovascularization process and to develop and test new therapeutic approaches for neovascularization [9]. It is also essential to determine the effectiveness of gene -, cell -, and cytokine - based therapies and implement results in clinical trials [10].

A suitable animal model for PAD should closely imitate pathological and functional characteristics of common human presentations and possess relevant human risk factors [11].

Our work aims to summarize the available animal models of ischemic limbs and to provide an overview of the advantages and disadvantages of each animal model and individual method of limb ischemia creation.

2. Methods

2.1. Search strategy

The PubMed and Web of Science pages were used to conduct a search for relevant papers. We chose not to limit the search according to publication date in order to attain as much information as possible. Research questions were defined as follows: “Which experimental animal models exist for limb ischemia?”, “What are the methods of limb ischemia creation/development in experimental animals?” (Fig. 1) The PICO elements (population, intervention, control, outcomes) with questions modified in preclinical context (animal, intervention, control group, outcomes) combined with Boolean operator “AND” were used for literature search. Both, small mammals (mice, rats, hamsters, guinea pigs, rabbits) and larger experimental animals (miniature pigs, pigs, dogs,

sheep, horses, non-human primates) were searched individually for relevant papers. References of included studies were examined to identify additional relevant papers.

2.2. Study selection

Inclusion criteria of studies were screened by two authors. Research papers, comparative studies, video articles, and reviews published in English with available full text were included. Titles and abstracts were screened to exclude irrelevant studies. Articles in language other than English, those with no full-text available (free and paid), and articles relating to ischemia-reperfusion injury, spinal cord ischemia, myocardial and cerebral ischemia, imaging methods research, and unrelated topic were excluded. Also, studies that dealt primarily with the various methods used to improve angiogenesis and ischemic tissue healing in animals were eliminated (Fig. 1). Important observations and findings from review articles were summarised in the discussion.

2.3. Data extraction

Data were extracted by two authors. The following outcome parameters of obtained articles were evaluated: type and number of experimental animals, age, weight, sex, specific animal characteristics, method of ischemic limb creation, and duration of tissue ischemia. Moreover, the aims and conclusions of individual works were highlighted in the summary table (Table 1).

2.4. Risk of bias and assessment of quality

We used SYRCLE's risk of bias tool for animal studies [12] for assessing quality of research papers, comparative studies and video articles. SANRA – a scale for the quality assessment of narrative review articles [13] - was applied for narrative reviews. The evaluation was carried out by two authors. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion with the senior author.

Research questions

“Which experimental animal models exist for limb ischemia?”, “What are the methods of limb ischemia creation/development in experimental animals?”

Inclusion criteria

Studies were included if the answer was “YES” to one or more of the following questions:

1. Does the study answer one of our research questions?
2. Is the main goal of the study to induce limb ischemia in experimental animal?
3. Is the study we are considering an overview of the animal experimental models of ischemic limbs described so far?
4. Does the study compare different animal models of limb ischemia?
5. Can be the full text of relevant study obtained and are the results of this study available?
6. Is the relevant study written in English?

Exclusion criteria

Studies were excluded if they met one or more of following criteria:

1. Studies that did not answer at least one of our research questions
2. Studies discussing the effect of different agents (gene -, cell -, and protein - based therapies) or different procedures improving blood flow to the ischemic limb in experimental animals
3. Studies discussing the topic of ischemia - reperfusion injury
4. Studies discussing the topic of spinal cord, myocardial, and cerebral ischemia
5. Studies discussing the topic of imaging method research in limb ischemia
6. Studies with available abstracts only
7. Studies with missing results
8. Studies with unrelated topic of interest
9. Studies written in language other than English

Fig. 1. Research questions. Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 1
Advantages and disadvantages of small and large experimental animals.

Animal	Advantages	Disadvantages
Rodents [11,15,43]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • accessibility • easy handle • low cost • require little space, food, and water • possibility to include large number of animals • statistical power of subsequent analyses • can be genetically altered to achieve disease states that are similar to those of humans e.g.: DBA/1 J mice are more prone to necrosis, BALB/c and ApoE^{-/-} mice are characterized by poor development of collaterals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • anatomical and physiological characteristics that are in contrast with the humans • small anatomical structures • the need to use a microscope in most cases • small muscle volume incomparable to human leg • rats naturally resist atherosclerotic development
Rabbit [25,41]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • intermediate size between rodents and larger animals • easy blood sampling and better access to many cells and tissues from one animal • longer life span than rodents • immune system genes of rabbits are apparently more similar to those of the human immune system • genetically modified species can develop atherosclerotic lesions under an appropriate fat regimen 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • more expensive than rodents • require more space and special cages
Pig [35,42]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • anatomical and physiological similarity to humans e.g.: similar anatomy of the hind limb vessels; skin is covered with individual coarse hairs rather than fur and is firmly attached to the underlying structures; biochemical structure of porcine collagen is similar to human collagen; the regeneration time of the porcine epidermis is approximately 30 days, the same as for the human epidermis • physiological and molecular responses to various growth factors similar to humans • sufficient size of anatomical structures • easier identification of blood vessels • no need to use a microscope • Ossabaw swine fed high fat diet can be utilized as model of metabolic syndrome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • possible ethical concerns • expensive • housing is more demanding • administering anaesthesia is more difficult and requires a skilled veterinarian • production of transgenic pigs is more difficult • use of a small number of animals in most cases • insufficient statistical power of subsequent analyses • porcine skin is less vascular • porcine skin has apocrine, not eccrine sweat glands • rapid collateral development
Sheep [42]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • anatomical and physiological similarity to humans • easy handle • relatively inexpensive with respect to housing and feeding • size (50–90 kg) is more similar to humans • size is ideal for testing surgical procedures or imaging modalities • sufficient size of anatomical structures • easier identification of blood vessels • no need to use a microscope 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • possible ethical concerns • housing is more demanding • administering anaesthesia is more difficult and requires a skilled veterinarian • use of a small number of animals in most cases • insufficient statistical power of subsequent analyses

3. Results

A total of 1590 and 1043 full text articles in English were identified when using PubMed and Web of Science pages, respectively. Thirty-three studies were found that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria (Fig. 2).

3.1. Type of experimental animal

Only the following animals met criteria described above: mice, rats, rabbits, miniature pigs, pigs, and sheep. Mice were the most used experimental animals [14–22], followed by rabbits [23–29], rats [10,30–33], pigs [34–38], miniature pigs [39], and sheep [40]. The advantages and disadvantages of each animal have been summarised in Table 1. Upon further searching, we found that studies of therapeutic angiogenesis and improvement of healing of ischemic limbs by various agents/methods have been performed mainly in mouse (805 studies), followed by rats (248 studies), rabbits (102 studies), pigs (6 studies), miniature pigs (1 study), and sheep (1 study).

3.2. Number of animals, sex, age, weight

The largest number of animals used was in the group of mice (average 43, Krishna et al. [22] 118), followed by rats (average 37, Zhuang et al. [31] 72), rabbits (average 19, Del Giudice et al. [27] 30), pigs (average 11, Nikol et al. [36] 20), miniature-pigs (average 11, Johnson et al. [39] 11), sheep (average 8, Margovsky et al. [40] 8). The male predominated in the mouse, rat and rabbit groups, while female predominated in the pigs. Almost all papers mentioned age and/or weight.

3.3. Specific animal characteristics

Twelve studies included various mice strains [15–18,22] and animals with specific characteristics such as immunodeficiency [10,17,20], diabetes [26,39], hyperlipidaemia [26,35], advanced age [34]. Outcomes for different animal models are presented in Table 1.

3.4. Methods of ischemic limb creation

There were one-stage (25 studies) and two-stage (3 studies) methods of limb ischemia creation described. One stage procedures comprised mostly single and double ligation of the femoral/iliac artery and excision of the entire femoral artery (FA) [10–15,23–26,34], ligation of common iliac, deep, and superficial femoral artery combined with excision of the segment from the external iliac to the common femoral artery [38], excision of the FA and/or femoral vein [16,20], single or double arterial electrocoagulation [17], use of ameroid constrictors [18,30], photochemically induced arterial thrombosis [19], embolization with hydrogel wire [31], arterial embolization using polyvinyl alcohol and N-butyl cyanoacrylate [32], arterial embolization using calibrated particles [27], radiofrequency ablation (RFA) of the superficial femoral artery [28], arterial embolization using endovascular coils [29], endovascular techniques using covered stents and vascular plugs [35,39], endovascular approach using detachable balloons, coils, and blinded stent-grafts [36,37], and microembolization using latex spherical microbeads [40]. Two stage methods represented sequential ligation of the femoral (day 0) and iliac (day 4) artery [21], interruption of collateral vessels originating from the infra-renal aorta and left iliac arteries (day 0) followed by ligation and division of the femoral artery (day 7) [33] and initial gradual femoral artery occlusion by ameroid constrictors for 14 days followed by subsequent arterial excision [22]. The advantages and disadvantages of each method have been

Fig. 2. Prisma flow diagram.

summarised in Table 2. Upon further searching for studies of therapeutic angiogenesis, we found that arterial ligation (347 studies) was the most commonly used surgical method of limb ischemia creation, followed by arterial excision (95 studies), arterial electrocoagulation (5 studies), and gradual occlusion using ameroid constrictors (5 studies). Arterial embolization (25 studies) was the most commonly used endovascular method of limb ischemia development, followed by the use of detachable balloons, coils, or blinded stent-grafts (10 studies), and radio-frequency ablation (1 study). The use of photochemically induced thrombosis has been described in 27 studies.

3.5. Duration of tissue ischemia

The shortest duration of tissue ischemia addressed was 7 days [19], the longest was 90 days [24]. Duration of tissue ischemia was not reported in six studies [14,18,32,36,37,40].

The summary outcomes of the different animal models are shown in Table 3.

3.6. Risk of bias and assessment of quality

Since most studies lacked basic items for assessing bias, such as missing data on randomization or blinding, it was difficult to validly assess these studies. It was often unclear, whether the data were not applied or their application was not reported. The risk of bias in each study has been summarised in Fig. 3. The plus sign (+) indicates low risk of bias, the minus sign (–) high risk of bias. The question mark (?) represents unclear risk of bias. The quality assessment of review articles has been summarised in Fig. 4. Overall, these were high quality articles. The biggest shortcoming was insufficiently described or missing search strategy of the literature used.

4. Discussion

The most commonly used experimental animals for limb ischemia research represent rodents and larger mammals. Mice and rats are easily available, due to low cost and easy handling, require less space, food and water, which enables researchers to include a relatively large number of animals [11]. The size of rabbits permits the simple blood sampling and greater access to many cells and tissues from a single animal. Additionally, rabbits have a longer life span than that of rodents, and the immune system genes are more similar to those of the humans [41]. Pigs and sheep have more human-like skin physiology, however, are significantly more expensive, and housing them is more demanding. Due to their size similar to human adults are widely used as models in organ transplantation and other surgical procedures [42].

Studies directed at the treatment of PAD commonly utilize preclinical models of disease.

Patients with cardiovascular disease, who participate in clinical trials, are typically older, with comorbidities such as diabetes, hypertension, and kidney disease and taking several medications. On the other hand, animals used for in vivo studies are often juvenile, of same age and health, and have no comorbidities [43]. Aging is associated with a loss of residency in our bodies ability to cope with a pathology. Serum growth hormone (GH) and insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) participate in multiple ways of the collateral vessel formation, remodelling, and arteriogenesis processes in ischemia. GH levels decline with increasing age. According to Deppen et al. [34], the lower levels of GH and IGF-1 may impair revascularization. Thus, the growth of blood vessels is very different in the pathophysiology model than in a normal juvenile model. Since there have been failed clinical trials on therapeutic angiogenesis (increased collateralization) based on studies on normal animals, interpretations of preclinical animal models should be confined to the given experimental situation and extrapolated with caution [11,44].

There is a need to conduct in vivo studies that incorporate risk factors

Table 2

Advantages and disadvantages of different methods of limb ischemia creation.

Method	Advantages	Disadvantages
Single arterial ligation of the femoral artery just distal to the origin of the profunda femoris artery [11,45]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> easy procedure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> acute induction of hind limb ischemia leaves most of the collateral circulation intact blood flow is fully restored within 7 days resembles acute ischemia or intermittent claudication rather than CLTI
transection of the proximal femoral artery at its bifurcation into the deep femoral artery [11]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> easy procedure removing of the collateral bed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> acute induction of hind limb ischemia risk of autoamputation of the limb in small mammals an unsuitable model for the study of CLTI
Multilevel arterial ligation [45]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> easy procedure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> acute induction of hind limb ischemia risk of rapid necrosis in small mammals risk of autoamputation of the limb in small mammals an unsuitable model for the study of CLTI
Ligation of the femoral artery and vein [11,45]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> easy procedure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> acute induction of hind limb ischemia patients with CLTI do not generally present with concurrent arterial and venous obstruction risk of autoamputation of the limb in small mammals
Total excision of the femoral artery + dissection of all side branches [9,11,17]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> easy procedure severe ischemia in the calf muscle suitable for studying angiogenesis in calf muscle duration of tissue ischemia up to 28 days suitable model for the study of CLTI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> acute induction of hind limb ischemia risk of severe toe/ft necrosis and/or limb paralysis in rodents
Triple ligation strategy in pigs – ligation of the unilateral external iliac artery combined with ligation of both internal iliac arteries [34]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> quite an easy procedure duration of tissue ischemia up to 42 days suitable model for the study of CLTI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> acute induction of hind limb ischemia requires skilled physician in most cases lack of research papers using this method
Ligation of the unilateral common iliac artery combined with ligation and excision of the external iliac and femoral artery, and ligation of the deep femoral and superficial femoral artery [38]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> quite an easy procedure duration of tissue ischemia up to 28 days suitable model for the study of CLTI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> acute induction of hind limb ischemia requires skilled physician in most cases lack of research papers using this method

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Table 2 (continued)

Method	Advantages	Disadvantages
Single arterial electrocoagulation [9,17]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • easy procedure • suitable for studying angiogenesis in calf muscle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • acute induction of hind limb ischemia • leaves most of the collateral circulation intact • blood flow is fully restored within 7 days
Double arterial electrocoagulation [9,17]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • easy procedure • suitable for studying angiogenesis in calf muscle • moderate ischemia • duration of tissue ischemia up to 28 days • suitable model for the study of CLTI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • acute induction of hind limb ischemia
sequential arterial ligation [21,33]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • easy procedure • sequential ligation resembles more of gradual occlusion • duration of tissue ischemia up to 30 days • suitable model for the study of CLTI • mimic human functional, clinical, scintigraphic, and skeletal muscle mitochondrial characteristics • low rate of oedema, inflammation, necrosis after 4 weeks resembles of CLTI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • acute induction of hind limb ischemia • risk of autoamputation of the limb in small mammals
Ameroid constrictors [9,18,22,30]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gradual arterial occlusion • leads to reduced treadmill performance and voluntary activity • lower expression of inflammatory and sheer stress-dependent genes • less muscle necrosis • slower blood flow recovery up to 4–5 weeks • suitable model for the study of CLTI 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • technical challenges – variable depth and shape of ameroid constrictors • possibility of inconsistent rates of occlusion and severity of ischemic limb injury
Endovascular methods [19,27–29,31,32,35–37,39,40]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • minimally invasive • none or minimal local tissue injury • protection of surrounding tissue from damage • long duration of tissue ischemia when using vascular stents combined with vascular plugs • long duration of tissue ischemia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • acute not progressive induction of hind limb ischemia • more complex procedure • requires skilled physician in most cases • embolization methods are more reminiscent of acute ischemia with short duration of tissue ischemia

Table 2 (continued)

Method	Advantages	Disadvantages
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • when using endovascular coils • long duration of tissue ischemia when using RFA • absence of the development of collateral vessels associated with wound healing rather than ischemia (typical for open surgery) 	
Photochemically induced thrombosis [19]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • minimally invasive • predictable illness trajectories • does not trigger side effects • no change in inflammation-related factors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • severe ischemia • risk of autoamputation of the limb in small mammals

similar to those seen in patients. According to Krishna et al. [11], dogs and rats naturally resist atherosclerotic development. Nevertheless, utilizing mice allows for genetic modification and dietary manipulation, and they can be exposed to cigarette smoke. Moreover, the extent of tissue necrosis resulting from limb ischemia in mice is dependent on strain. For example, DBA/1 J mice are more prone to necrosis than are C57BL/6 or BALB/c mice. BALB/c and apolipoprotein E deficient mice (ApoE^{-/-} mice) are characterized by their poor development of collateral arteries [11,15]. ApoE^{-/-} mice experience delayed skeletal muscle healing, reduced angiogenesis, and impaired functional recovery after hindlimb ischemia, which is reminiscent of mechanisms in PAD patients [11]. The use of animals with artificially created diabetes or hyperlipidaemia provides another advantage. Sligar et al. [26] utilized alloxan injections and a high fat diet in order to create a model of ischemia in rabbits with diabetes and hyperlipidaemia. In the diabetes group, blood flow gradually decreased over a 70-day period. Using an endovascular plug, Johnson et al. [39] created a model of limb ischemia in diabetic mini-pigs that led to a stable decrease in blood perfusion for 28 days. There were also fewer collaterals in the diabetic group, indicating that diabetes suppressed collateral vessel formation in response to arterial occlusion. A similar finding – impaired arteriogenic response (also seen in human metabolic syndrome) - was described by Long et al. [35] when using Ossabaw swine that were fed a high-fat diet.

In PAD in vivo models, the severity of ischemia is dependent on two factors: the length and location of arterial occlusion and the capacity for collateral development [45]. Ligation carried out in close proximity to the aorta, as well as ligation of potential collateral vessels, can lead to more severe ischemia than would result from superficial distal occlusion [46]. Unfortunately, current in vivo models of limb ischemia are primarily those of acute limb ischemia. They do not mimic the gradual, chronic occlusion and decrease in blood flow observed in patients with PAD. Acute limb ischemia induced by FA ligation can result in tissue necrosis and make it challenging to study vascular and skeletal muscle tissue responses to ischemia [19]. Single ligation is a commonly used method carried out by ligating the FA just distal to the origin of profunda femoris. This technique is easy but leaves most of the collateral circulation intact, and blood flow is fully restored within seven days after surgery. Double ligation of the FA produces more severe ischemia. Multilevel arterial ligation in rodents can lead to necrosis and autoamputation of the limb [47]. According to Hellingman et al. [17], single coagulation restored blood flow within 7 days post-surgery. In contrast, the implementation of double electrocoagulation brought about a delay in blood flow restoration.

Table 3
Available animal experimental models of ischemic limbs.

Author	Animal Number	Sex	Age Weight	Animal characteristics	Method of ischemic limb creation	Aim of study	Duration of ischemia	Conclusion
Niiyama et al. [14]	Mouse 1	NA*	NA	mice (unknown strain)	ligation and excision of the entire femoral artery (FA)	to create a murine model of limb ischemia	not measured	dramatic reduction in blood flow in the ischemic limb immediately after surgery
Parikh et al. [15]	Mouse NA	M	8–10 weeks NA	BALB/c vs. FVB vs. C57BL/6 strain	double ligation of the FA	to develop a model of limb gangrene	28 days	the use of various mice strain may influence the progression of ischemia
Goto et al. [16]	Mouse 75	M	12 weeks 20-30 g	BALB/c strain	six various surgical methods	to find a standard method of ischemic limb creation	14 days	stripping the entire femoral artery produced severe stable ischemia
Hellingman et al. [17]	Mouse 27	M	10–12 weeks NA	C57BL/6 strain vs. Immune-deficient NOD-scid IL2Rgamma (null) mice	single electrocoagulation of the femoral and iliac artery vs. total excision of FA vs. double electrocoagulation of both the iliac and FA	to identify an optimal model of limb ischemia	28 days	cutting the femoral artery just below the bifurcation site of the deep femoral artery produced chronic mild ischemia
Padgett et al. [18]	Mouse NA	M	NA NA	BALB/c vs. C57BL/6 strain	ligation and transection of the FA vs. gradual occlusion with ameroid constrictors	to highlight the influence of genetic background in acute and subacute limb ischemia models	not measured	delay in blood flow restoration when using double electrocoagulation model
Han et al. [19]	Mouse 30	M	8 weeks 35-45 g	ICR mice	ligation of the external iliac artery (EIA) and double ligation of the FA vs. photochemically induced arterial thrombosis	to develop a model of limb ischemia similar to human peripheral arterial disease	7 days	BALB/c (not C57BL/6) mice displayed significant muscle necrosis despite employing the gradual occlusion method
Shimatani et al. [20]	Mouse 25	M	6–8 weeks NA	NOG-mice	excision of the entire FA and vein (Type-C) vs. excision of the entire FA and vein + dissection and cutting lateral marginal vein (Type-N)	to create a model of chronic limb ischemia by increasing the excised area of blood vessels	63 days	the extent of limb muscle injury is influenced by genetic background
Lejay et al. [21]	Mouse 28	M	NA 30-35 g	Swiss mice	sequential ligation of the femoral and iliac artery	to establish a chronic model of limb ischemia mimicking human pathology	30 days	symptoms were more uniform using photochemically induced thrombosis model
Krishna et al. [22]	Mouse 118	M	20 months NA	Apo E−/− mice	double ligation and excision of the FA vs. gradual occlusion of the FA with ameroid constrictors and subsequent arterial excision (2-stage model)	to examine a two-stage limb ischemia model designed to mimic human peripheral arterial disease	28 days	non-invasive method resulted in fewer side effects than did surgical ligation
Hendricks et al. [23]	Rabbit 20	M/F	NA NA	New Zealand rabbits	ligation and division of the common iliac artery	to develop a model of partial persistent limb ischemia	38 days	Type-N resembled chronic and severe limb ischemia model with impaired angiogenesis that did not show restoration in blood flow for 9 weeks
Pu et al. [24]	Rabbit 28	M	NA 4 kg	New Zealand rabbits	ligation of the EIA and excision of the entire FA	to develop a model of persistent limb ischemia	90 days	gradual arterial occlusion led to a valid chronic limb ischemia model with impaired in vivo and ex vivo function
Hong et al. [25]	Rabbit 8	M	2–2.8 kg NA	New Zealand rabbits	excision of the entire FA	to create a model of limb ischemia for the research of new treatment modalities	42 days	reduced limb perfusion in the 2-stage model by day 28

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Table 3 (continued)

Author	Animal Number	Sex	Age Weight	Animal characteristics	Method of ischemic limb creation	Aim of study	Duration of ischemia	Conclusion
Sligar et al. [26]	Rabbit NA	NA	4–6 months NA	New Zealand rabbits with hyperlipidemia and diabetes	excision of the entire FA	to compare a model of limb ischemia in rabbits with diabetes and hyperlipidemia to that in non-diabetic rabbits fed a high fat diet and to observe their influence on collateral vessel formation	56 days	stress on the liver and faster blood pressure recovery in the non-diabetic group fed a high cholesterol diet (1%) persistent decreases in blood pressure as well as deficits in collateral vessel formation in the diabetic group fed a diet lower in cholesterol (0.1%)
Del Giudice et al. [27]	Rabbit 30	NA	NA 4.5–5.5 kg	New Zealand rabbits	arterial embolization with calibrated particles	to provide a critical limb ischemia model with ulcers and rest pain	14 days	higher pain score and development of limb ulcers in all animals decreased blood flow to the ischemic limb for 14 days
Baik et al. [28]	Rabbit 9	M	NA 3–4 kg	New Zealand rabbits	radiofrequency ablation (RFA) of the superficial femoral artery	to establish a model of limb ischemia using RFA	30 days	more developed collaterals by day 42 post-RFA persistent decrease in blood flow and blood volume for 30 days
Liddell et al. [29]	Rabbit 17	M	NA 2.5–3.2 kg	New Zealand rabbits	embolization of the superficial femoral artery through the use of endovascular coils vs. surgical ligation	to demonstrate that the endovascular method serves as a more appropriate model of limb ischemia than does surgical ligation	28 days	endovascular model induced less of an arteriogenic response (enlargement of distal profunda femoris artery) decrease in blood pressure observed on day 28 in both groups with no statistical difference between groups
Yang et al. [10]	Rat 18	M	4 weeks NA	athymic rnu-rats (NIH-Foxn1rnu)	double ligation of the FA	to create a model of persistent limb ischemia	60 days	decreased vascularization and muscle mitochondrial function lack of fibrosis and tissue necrosis in ischemic limb after 4 weeks
Tang et al. [30]	Rat 42	M	NA 280–350 g	Sprague-Dawley rats	ligation of the common iliac and FA vs. gradual occlusion with ameroid constrictors	to compare the effects of acute and chronic ischemia on skeletal muscle	40 days	slower recovery of dermal blood flow and no evidence of muscle necrosis, fibrosis or inflammation when implementing gradual occlusion method with ameroid constrictors
Zhuang et al. [31]	Rat 72	M	10–12 weeks 250–275 g	Lewis rats	ligation and excision of the entire FA vs. arterial embolization with hydrogel wire	to develop a mini-interventional model of limb ischemia and compare its angiogenic effects to those of a surgical ligation model	14 days	mini-interventional limb ischemia model preserved tissue integrity and minimized inflammation and damage of surrounding tissue
Shin et al. [32]	Rat 12	M	10–12 weeks 350–400 g	Sprague-Dawley rats	double ligation and transection of the EIA vs. arterial embolization with polyvinyl alcohol vs. N-butyl cyanoacrylate	to examine the feasibility of embolization as a method to induce limb ischemia	not measured	embolization methods resembled acute arterial occlusion muscle infarction and inflammation were spotted near the infarcted areas in the embolization group
Lundberg et al. [33]	Rat 40	M	NA 245 g	Sprague-Dawley rats	ligation of the collateral vessels originating from the infra-renal aorta and left iliac arteries followed by ligation and division of the FA	to develop a model of severe limb ischemia	56 days	gradual arterial occlusion led to development of a long-term limb ischemia model with low rate of oedema, inflammation, necrosis and fibrosis after 4 weeks
Deppen et al. [34]	Pig 13	F/M 12:1	NA 45–58 kg	Yorkshire swine (young vs. old)	ligation of the unilateral EIA vs. ligation of the EIA and unilateral internal iliac artery (IIA) vs. “triple” ligation of both IIA and unilateral EIA (in young vs. old animals)	to create a large animal model of limb ischemia	42 days	a decrease in systolic blood pressure observed 6 weeks post-surgery when using “triple” ligation method extended gait dysfunction after “triple” ligation method in the group comprising older pigs exercise-induced perfusion

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Author	Animal Number	Sex	Age Weight	Animal characteristics	Method of ischemic limb creation	Aim of study	Duration of ischemia	Conclusion
Long et al. [35]	Yorkshire pig 8 Ossabaw Pig 8	F	6–8 months 52.9 kg	Yorkshire swine vs. Ossabaw swine	endovascular approach using covered stents and vascular plugs	to create a large model of limb ischemia that mimics the condition in patients with severe peripheral arterial disease	42 days	deficit characteristics observed in the “triple” ligation group (after infusion of adenosine) similar to those seen in human peripheral arterial disease increased ischemic myopathy in the ischemic limb gradual decrease in blood pressure for 6 weeks post-surgery diminished arteriogenic response in Ossabaw swine
Nikol et al. [36]	Pig 20	NA	NA 35 kg	Pietrain pigs	endovascular approach using detachable balloons vs. coils vs. blinded stent-grafts	to provide an endovascular model of long-term arterial occlusion	not measured	complete occlusion after 6 months when using blinded stent-grafts no difference in collateral vessel formation between the endovascular arterial occlusion group and non-occluded controls
Engelmann et al. [37]	Pig 11	NA	NA 35 kg	Pietrain pigs	ligation and transection of the FA vs. endovascular approach using blinded stent-grafts	to compare an endovascular technique to surgical approach to achieve long-term arterial occlusion	not measured	collateral formation post-surgery may be associated with wound healing rather than ischemia no significant angiogenesis was observed by using endovascular approach
Samatoshenkov et al. [38]	Pig 4	F	3-4 months 8-12 kg	Vietnamese pot-bellied pigs	ligation of the common iliac artery, ligation and excision of the EIA and FA, ligation of the deep femoral and superficial femoral artery	to develop and examine model of limb ischemia	28 days	decreased blood pressure and oxygen saturation for 28 days decreased temperature of the ischemic limb, increased lactate and creatine phosphokinase right after surgery decreased number of blood vessels, increased connective tissue area
Johnson et al. [39]	Miniature pig 11	M	NA 27-30 kg	Yucatan mini-pigs (non-diabetic vs. purpose-bred diabetic)	endovascular approach using vascular plugs	to highlight angiogenic responses to limb ischemia in diabetic vs. non-diabetic animals	28 days	no increase in perfusion between day 1 and 28 in the diabetic group diminished collateral vessel formation in the diabetic group
Margovsky et al. [40]	Sheep 8	F	NA 50-60 kg	sheep	latex microbead arterial embolization	to create a model of limb ischemia in order to study the pathophysiology and treatment of small vessel disease	not measured	decreasing arterial pressure with increasing number of microbeads angiograms indicated obstruction of multiple small vessels no filling defects revealed in the femoral, popliteal or tibial arteries

* NA, Not Available.

Since most collaterals arise from the internal iliac artery, sequential arterial ligation at intervals of several days (e.g.: ligation of the iliac artery followed by ligation of the femoral artery) can lead to a reduction in collateral perfusion [21]. Ameroid constrictors consist of an external metal sleeve and inner hygroscopic material (primarily casein). When the constrictor is placed around the artery, it induces gradual vessel occlusion by absorbing moisture from the surrounding tissue. This mechanism leads to reduced inflammatory gene expression, slower blood flow recovery, and minor muscle necrosis [18]. Nevertheless, Padgett et al. [18] stated that one single method for inducing limb ischemia may not be suitable in all cases. In this study, the use of ameroid constrictors in BALB/c mice, which are more ischemia-susceptible, led to subacute rather than gradual ischemia. According

to Engelmann et al. [37], the development of collateral vessels may be associated with wound healing rather than ischemia. When authors used endovascular methods, no significant angiogenesis was observed. In addition, endovascular approach protected surrounding artery, nerves or veins from damage [31].

It is essential to monitor the duration of tissue ischemia in order to assess whether it is acute, subacute, or chronic. A suitable model of chronic limb ischemia similar to that seen in human should have duration of ischemia at least 2 weeks. According to Conte et al. [48] chronic limb-threatening ischemia represents a clinical syndrome defined by the presence of peripheral artery disease in combination with rest pain, gangrene, or a lower limb ulceration >2 weeks duration. However, it would be optimal to maintain ischemia at least 4 weeks due to dramatic

SYRCLÉ's risk of bias tool for animal studies

Author	Selection bias			Performance bias		Detection bias		Attrition bias	Reporting bias	Other
	Sequence generation	Baseline characteristics	Allocation concealment	Random housing	Blinding	Random outcome assessment	Blinding	Incomplete outcome data	Selective outcome reporting	Other sources of bias
Niyama et al. *†	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?	?
Parikh et al.	?	+	?	?	?	?	?	+	+	-
Goto et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	?
Hellingman et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	-
Padgett et al. *	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	?	+	-
Han et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	?
Shimatani et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	?	-	-
Lejay et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	-
Krishna et al.	?	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	?
Hendricks et al.	?	-	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	-
Pu et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	-
Hong et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	-
Sligar et al. *	?	?	?	?	-	?	?	?	+	-
Del Giudice et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	-
Baik et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	?
Liddell et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	-
Yang et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	?
Tang et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	†	-	+	-
Zhuang et al.	?	+	+	?	-	+	?	+	+	?
Shin et al.	-	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	-
Lundberg et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	-
Deppen et al.	?	-	?	?	-	?	?	+	-	-
Long et. Al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	-
Nikol et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	?
Engelmann et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	?
Samatoshenkov et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	+	+	-
Johnson et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	?	+	?
Margovsky et al.	?	+	?	?	-	?	?	-	+	-

■ low risk
 ■ unclear risk
 ■ high risk

*video articles

†demonstration of the methodology for the murine model of unilateral hindlimb ischemia in one animal only

‡observers were blinded when examining angiograms; missing information on blinding when assessing other parameters

Fig. 3. SYRCLÉ's risk of bias tool for animal studies.

Scale for the Assessment of Narrative Review Articles - SANRA					
	Aref et al.	Krishna et al.	Madeddu et al.	Waters et al.	Lofti et al.
1. Justification of the article's importance for the readership	2	2	2	2	2
2. Statement of concrete aims or formulation of questions	2	2	2	2	2
3. Description of the literature search	0	0	0	0	0
4. Referencing	2	2	1	1	2
5. Scientific reasoning	2	2	2	2	2
6. Appropriate presentation of data	2	2	2	2	2
Sumscore	10	10	9	9	10
0 – 2 (0 – low quality, 2 – high quality)					

Fig. 4. Scale for the assessment of narrative review articles – SANRA.

endogenous compensation mechanisms resulting from acute ischemia within 4 weeks post-surgery, which can lead to deteriorated evaluations of therapeutic angiogenesis [10].

5. Conclusions

Taking into consideration the information presented above, we feel that a suitable animal model for limb ischemia should be as anatomically and physiologically similar to humans as possible. The animal should be sufficiently large in size, and it should possess specific human comorbidities. A two-stage sequential approach and methods using ameroid constrictors or endovascular blinded stent grafts are more suitable for creating a gradual arterial occlusion typically seen in humans. Selecting the right mouse strain or animal with artificially produced diabetes or hyperlipidaemia is crucial in chronic ischemic limb research. Moreover, the observation period following the onset of ischemia should have a duration of at least 14 days, preferably 4 weeks. Although many variations have been described, acquiring an optimal model of a chronic ischemic limb that accurately resembles human pathology remains a significant challenge.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Veronika Lovasova: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Robert Bem:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Jaroslav Chlupac:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Michal Dubsky:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Jitka Husakova:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Andrea Nemcova:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Jiri Fronck:** Project administration, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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References

- [1] S. Duff, M.S. Mafilios, P. Bhounsule, J.T. Hasegawa, The burden of critical limb ischemia: a review of recent literature, *Vasc. Health Risk Manag.* 15 (2019) 187–208, <https://doi.org/10.2147/VHRM.S209241>.
- [2] S. Kinlay, Management of critical limb ischemia, *Circ. Cardiovasc. Interv.* 9 (2) (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCINTERVENTIONS.115.001946> e001946.
- [3] M. Qadura, D.C. Terenzi, S. Verma, M. Al-Omran, D.A. Hess, Concise review: cell therapy for critical limb ischemia: an integrated review of preclinical and clinical studies, *Stem Cells* 36 (2) (2018) 161–171, <https://doi.org/10.1002/stem.2751>.
- [4] T. Thiruvoipati, C.E. Kielhorn, E.J. Armstrong, Peripheral artery disease in patients with diabetes: epidemiology, mechanisms, and outcomes, *World J. Diabetes* 6 (7) (2015) 961–969, <https://doi.org/10.4239/wjcd.v6.i7.961>.
- [5] K. Alexiadou, J. Doupis, Management of diabetic foot ulcers, *Diabetes Ther.* 3 (1) (2012) 4, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13300-012-0004-9>.
- [6] L. Prompers, N. Schaper, J. Apelqvist, M. Edmonds, E. Jude, D. Mauricio, et al., Prediction of outcome in individuals with diabetic foot ulcers: focus on the differences between individuals with and without peripheral arterial disease. The EURODIABE Study, *Diabetologia* 51 (5) (2008) 747–755, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-008-0940-0>.
- [7] J. Gorecka, V. Kostiuik, A. Fereydooni, L. Gonzalez, J. Luo, B. Dash, et al., The potential and limitations of induced pluripotent stem cells to achieve wound healing, *Stem Cell Res Ther* 10 (1) (2019) 87. Published 2019 Mar 12, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13287-019-1185-1>.
- [8] H. Lawall, P. Bramlage, B. Amann, Treatment of peripheral arterial disease using stem and progenitor cell therapy, *J. Vasc. Surg.* 53 (2) (2011) 445–453, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2010.08.060>.
- [9] Z. Aref, M.R. de Vries, P.H.A. Quax, Variations in surgical procedures for inducing hind limb ischemia in mice and the impact of these variations on neovascularization assessment, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 20 (15) (2019) 3704. Published 2019 Jul 29, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20153704>.
- [10] Z. Yang, M.W. von Ballmoos, N. Diehm, I. Baumgartner, C. Kalka, S. Di Santo, Call for a reference model of chronic hind limb ischemia to investigate therapeutic angiogenesis, *Vasc. Pharmacol.* 51 (4) (2009) 268–274, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vph.2009.07.001>.

- [11] S.M. Krishna, S.M. Omer, J. Golledge, Evaluation of the clinical relevance and limitations of current pre-clinical models of peripheral artery disease, *Clin. Sci. (Lond.)* 130 (3) (2016) 127–150, <https://doi.org/10.1042/CS20150435>.
- [12] C.R. Hooijmans, M.M. Roovers, R.B. de Vries, M. Leenaars, M. Ritskes-Hoitinga, M. W. Langendam, SYRCL's risk of bias tool for animal studies, *BMC Med. Res. Methodol.* 14 (2014) 43, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-14-43>.
- [13] C. Baethge, S. Goldbeck-Wood, S. Mertens, SANRA-a scale for the quality assessment of narrative review articles, *Res. Integr. Peer Rev.* 4 (2019) 5, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41073-019-0064-8>.
- [14] H. Niiyama, N.F. Huang, M.D. Rollins, J.P. Cooke, Murine model of hindlimb ischemia, *J. Vis. Exp.* 23 (2009) 1035, <https://doi.org/10.3791/1035>.
- [15] P.P. Parikh, D. Castilla, R.M. Lassance-Soares, H. Shao, M. Regueiro, Y. Li, et al., A reliable mouse model of hind limb gangrene, *Ann. Vasc. Surg.* 48 (2018) 222–232, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avsg.2017.10.008>.
- [16] T. Goto, N. Fukuyama, A. Aki, K. Kanabuchi, K. Kimura, H. Taira, et al., Search for appropriate experimental methods to create stable hind-limb ischemia in mouse, *Tokai J. Exp. Clin. Med.* 31 (3) (2006) 128–132.
- [17] A.A. Hellingman, A.J. Bastiaansen, M.R. de Vries, L. Seghers, M.A. Lijkwan, C. H. Löwik, et al., Variations in surgical procedures for hind limb ischaemia mouse models result in differences in collateral formation, *Eur. J. Vasc. Endovasc. Surg.* 40 (6) (2010) 796–803, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejvs.2010.07.009>.
- [18] M.E. Padgett, T.J. McCord, J.M. McClung, C.D. Kontos, Methods for acute and subacute murine Hindlimb ischemia, *J. Vis. Exp.* 112 (2016) 54166, <https://doi.org/10.3791/54166>.
- [19] S.S. Han, Z. Jin, B.S. Lee, J.S. Han, J.J. Choi, S.J. Park, et al., Reproducible hindlimb ischemia model based on photochemically induced thrombosis to evaluate angiogenic effects, *Microvasc. Res.* 126 (2019) 103912, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mvr.2019.103912>.
- [20] K. Shimatani, H. Sato, A. Saito, M. Sasai, K. Watanabe, K. Mizukami, et al., A novel model of chronic limb ischemia to therapeutically evaluate the angiogenic effects of drug candidates, *Am. J. Physiol. Heart Circ. Physiol.* 320 (3) (2021) H1124–H1135, <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.00470.2020>.
- [21] A. Lejay, P. Choquet, F. Thaveau, F. Singh, A. Schlagowski, A.L. Charles, et al., A new murine model of sustainable and durable chronic critical limb ischemia fairly mimicking human pathology, *Eur. J. Vasc. Endovasc. Surg.* 49 (2) (2015) 205–212, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejvs.2014.12.010>.
- [22] S.M. Krishna, S.M. Omer, J. Li, S.K. Morton, R.J. Jose, J. Golledge, Development of a two-stage limb ischemia model to better simulate human peripheral artery disease, *Sci. Rep.* 10 (1) (2020) 3449, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-60352-4>.
- [23] D.L. Hendricks, W.C. Pevec, K.C. Shestak, M.C. Rosenthal, M.W. Webster, D. L. Steed, A model of persistent partial hindlimb ischemia in the rabbit, *J. Vasc. Res.* 49 (5) (1990) 453–457, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4804\(90\)90195-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-4804(90)90195-8).
- [24] L.Q. Pu, S. Jackson, K.J. Lachapelle, Z. Arekat, A.M. Graham, R. Lisbona, et al., A persistent hindlimb ischemia model in the rabbit, *J. Invest. Surg.* 7 (1) (1994) 49–60, <https://doi.org/10.3109/08941939409018282>.
- [25] J.H. Hong, Y.W. Bahk, J.S. Suh, B.K. Kwak, H.J. Shim, J.S. Kim, et al., An experimental model of ischemia in rabbit hindlimb, *J. Korean Med. Sci.* 16 (5) (2001) 630–635, <https://doi.org/10.3346/jkms.2001.16.5.630>.
- [26] A.D. Sligar, G. Howe, J. Goldman, P. Felli, V. Karanam, R.W. Smalling, A.B. Baker, Preclinical model of hind limb ischemia in diabetic rabbits, *J. Vis. Exp.* 148 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.3791/58964>.
- [27] C. Del Giudice, G. Ifergan, G. Goudot, V. Bellamy, E. Messas, O. Clement, et al., Evaluation of a new model of hind limb ischemia in rabbits, *J. Vasc. Surg.* 68 (3) (2018) 849–857, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2017.07.140>.
- [28] H.W. Baik, B.K. Kwak, H.J. Shim, Y.S. Kim, J.B. Lee, K.S. Kim, A new ischemic model using a radiofrequency wire electrode in a rabbit hindlimb, *Cardiovasc. Intervent. Radiol.* 31 (4) (2008) 790–798, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00270-008-9302-z>.
- [29] R.P. Liddell, T.H. Patel, C.R. Weiss, D.S. Lee, T. Matsushashi, P.R. Brown, et al., Endovascular model of rabbit hindlimb ischemia: a platform to evaluate therapeutic angiogenesis, *J. Vasc. Interv. Radiol.* 16 (7) (2005) 991–998, <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.RVI.0000161381.48445.48>.
- [30] G.L. Tang, D.S. Chang, R. Sarkar, R. Wang, L.M. Messina, The effect of gradual or acute arterial occlusion on skeletal muscle blood flow, arteriogenesis, and inflammation in rat hindlimb ischemia, *J. Vasc. Surg.* 41 (2) (2005) 312–320, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2004.11.012>.
- [31] Z.W. Zhuang, J. Shi, J.M. Rhodes, M.J. Tsapakos, M. Simons, Challenging the surgical rodent hindlimb ischemia model with the mini-interventional technique, *J. Vasc. Interv. Radiol.* 22 (10) (2011) 1437–1446, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvir.2010.12.039>.
- [32] C.I. Shin, H.C. Kim, Y.S. Song, H.R. Cho, K.B. Lee, W. Lee, et al., Rat model of hindlimb ischemia induced by embolization with polyvinyl alcohol and N-butyl cyanoacrylate, *Korean J. Radiol.* 14 (6) (2013) 923–930, <https://doi.org/10.3348/kjr.2013.14.6.923>.
- [33] G. Lundberg, F. Luo, H. Blegen, B. Kalin, E. Wahlberg, A rat model for severe limb ischemia at rest, *Eur. Surg. Res.* 35 (5) (2003) 430–438, <https://doi.org/10.1159/000072228>.
- [34] J.N. Deppen, S.C. Ginn, N.H. Kim, L. Wang, R.J. Voll, S.H. Liang, et al., A swine hind limb ischemia model useful for testing peripheral artery disease therapeutics, *J. Cardiovasc. Transl. Res.* 14 (6) (2021) 1186–1197, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12265-021-10134-8>.
- [35] C.A. Long, L.H. Timmins, P. Koutakis, T.T. Goodchild, D.J. Lefer, I.I. Pipinos, et al., An endovascular model of ischemic myopathy from peripheral arterial disease, *J. Vasc. Surg.* 66 (3) (2017) 891–901, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2016.07.127>.
- [36] S. Nikol, S. Armeanu, M.G. Engelmann, J. Pelisek, A. Fuchs, C. Zähringer, et al., Evaluation of endovascular techniques for creating a porcine femoral artery occlusion model, *J. Endovasc. Ther.* 8 (4) (2001) 401–407, <https://doi.org/10.1177/152660280100800409>.
- [37] M.G. Engelmann, M. Shimizu, J. Pelisek, A. Fuchs, A. Golda, C. Mekkaoui, et al., Comparison of surgical versus endovascular occlusion models in pig femoral arteries, *J. Endovasc. Ther.* 11 (1) (2004) 71–79, <https://doi.org/10.1177/152660280401100109>.
- [38] I. Samatoshenkov, I. Krasivskyi, I. Djordjevic, B. Ivanov, J. Merkle, A. Sakhigareeva, et al., New experimental model of hind limb ischemia in pot-bellied pigs, *Microvasc. Res.* 145 (2023) 104425, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mvr.2022.104425>.
- [39] L.L. Johnson, J. Johnson, Z. Ali, Y. Tekabe, R. Ober, G. Geist, et al., VEGF receptor targeted imaging of angiogenic response to limb ischemia in diabetic vs. non-diabetic Yucatan minipigs, *EJNMMI Res.* 10 (1) (2020) 48, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13550-020-00626-0>.
- [40] A. Margovsky, Y.V. Bobryshev, A.J. Chambers, J. Iliopoulos, R.S. Lord, Small vessel ischaemia induced by microbead embolization in the sheep hind limb, *Aust. N. Z. J. Surg.* 68 (8) (1998) 592–598, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1445-2197.1998.tb02107.x>.
- [41] P.J. Esteves, J. Abrantes, H.M. Baldauf, L. BenMohamed, Y. Chen, N. Christensen, et al., The wide utility of rabbits as models of human diseases, *Exp. Mol. Med.* 50 (5) (2018) 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s12276-018-0094-1>.
- [42] I. Ribitsch, P.M. Baptista, A. Lange-Consiglio, L. Melotti, M. Patruno, F. Jenner, et al., Large animal models in regenerative medicine and tissue engineering: to do or not to do, *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 8 (2020) 972, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2020.00972>.
- [43] K. McCafferty, S. Forbes, C. Thiemermann, M.M. Yaqoob, The challenge of translating ischemic conditioning from animal models to humans: the role of comorbidities, *Dis. Model. Mech.* 7 (12) (2014 Dec) 1321–1333, <https://doi.org/10.1242/dmm.016741>.
- [44] J.P. Cooke, S. Meng, Vascular regeneration in peripheral artery disease, *Arterioscler. Thromb. Vasc. Biol.* 40 (7) (2020 Jul) 1627–1634, <https://doi.org/10.1161/ATVBAHA.120.312862>.
- [45] P. Madeddu, C. Emanuelli, F. Spillmann, M. Meloni, N. Bouby, C. Richer, et al., Murine models of myocardial and limb ischemia: diagnostic end-points and relevance to clinical problems, *Vasc. Pharmacol.* 45 (5) (2006) 281–301, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vph.2006.08.008>.
- [46] R.E. Waters, R.L. Terjung, K.G. Peters, B.H. Annex, Preclinical models of human peripheral arterial occlusive disease: implications for investigation of therapeutic agents, *J. Appl. Physiol.* 97 (2) (2004) 773–780, <https://doi.org/10.1152/japplphysiol.00107.2004>.
- [47] S. Lotfi, A.S. Patel, K. Mattock, S. Egginton, A. Smith, B. Modarai, Towards a more relevant hind limb model of muscle ischaemia, *Atherosclerosis.* 227 (1) (2013) 1–8, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atherosclerosis.2012.10.060>.
- [48] M.S. Conte, A.W. Bradbury, P. Kolh, J.V. White, F. Dick, R. Fitridge, GVG Writing Group, et al., Global vascular guidelines on the management of chronic limb-threatening ischemia, *J. Vasc. Surg.* 69 (6S) (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvs.2019.02.016>, 3S–125S.e40.